

Linear Programming Formulation of Relu Function

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1 Introduction

Relu function (see figure 1) is a non-linear function. But if we formulate it as a hard constraint in linear programming, we can make it becomes a convex optimization problem as linear programming is convex.

If we will to imagine Relu function as a linear inequality in linear programming, it will look something like figure 2, where green strips mark the invalid region. If we look at an example of feasible region in linear programming in figure 3, it will contains a few lines of inequalities where green strips mark the invalid regions. So in a BSnet Relu network (see paper [3, 2, 1]), the Relu activation functions will act like inequalities and the BSnet can be represented by linear programming. The linear transform by the weights in a layer in BSnet will reorientate the inequality hyperplane in the linear programming.

2 Model

The linear programming formulation of Relu function will look as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_y \quad & y \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & y \geq x, \\ & y \geq 0. \end{aligned}$$

The variable x is input of Relu function, y is output of Relu function. We can see that if $x \leq 0$, y is always 0. But when $x > 0$, $y = x$.

$y \geq x$ and $y \geq 0$ are the linear equalities for the linear programming of one neuron Relu function. We can combine linear programming of all neurons in a BSnet into one linear programming.

So this is the formulation for only 1 neuron. We have to combine linear programming of all neurons in a layer, and all layers, with the softmax function to form an overall convex optimization formulation.

Figure 1: Relu function

Figure 2: Relu function, where green strips mark the invalid region by linear inequality of linear programming

3 Future Works

My plan is to later formulate the whole BSnet (see paper [3, 2, 1]) as linear programming and convex optimization problem. In this way I can prove that my BSnet is convex.

This bridges the theory to Support Vector Machine and Linear Programming. The weights distribution of BSnet is similar and related to Lagrange variables distribution in Support Vector Machine dual formulation.

This also explains that the use of non-threshold activation function (example of threshold function is Relu function) like softplus will break the linear programming properties, and thus breaks convexity. So my approach to convert any existing deep learning network to BSnet layers, I will replace sigmoid, softplus and other non-threshold activation functions to Relu function, except that I will keep softmax loss at the final layer. To know whether the conversion of the network is convex, we check whether the gradient descent is smooth during

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Figure 3: Example of a feasible region with a few linear inequality. Green strips mark the invalid region and red marks the valid region

training, do dimension reduction on the loss function and visualize it to see if it is convex, add Gaussian noise or blur noise during inference to see if it is robust to the noise due to convexity, and do adversarial noise attack on the network to see if the noise is non-random with strong edge detection image in the noise due to convexity. Note that the trained weights and intermediate outputs are sparse instead of dense (means they contain a lot of zeros) due to convexity of training loss. And the visualization of intermediate layer feature maps is more crisp with more details.

Due to the convexity of BSnet, there is no need to add regularization such as weight decay to smooth and stabilise the gradient descent during training.

I think pooling layers will not make it non-convex, which no need to change. But residual addition links in Resnet will break the Boolean structured of BSnet and so that have to be replaced by a BSnet equivalent links. Attention layers will break the convexity as attention layer is the product sum of 2 functions. So my approach is to convert product sum of 2 functions to sum of product of 2 functions by doing a complement operation.

Sum pooling is the summation of two or more convex functions which is also convex. For max pooling, the max sum of two or more convex functions are convex mathematically.

If the deep learning network is non-convex, it will learn to fit the FlashOcc and Pidnet deep learning network segmentations by patches instead of whole.

4 Conclusion

Deep learning started as an experimental science with no theory to explain why and how it works. Knowing why enables us to fix drawbacks in the network and redesigns the network from scratch as existing deep learning network is inherently flawed.

References

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